

The Use of Facebook as a Social Media by Political Parties in the June 7 Election in Konya

Yasemin Gülşen Yılmaz, Süleyman Hakan Yılmaz, Muhammet Erbay

Abstract—Social media is among the most important means of communication. Social media offers individuals and groups with an opportunity for participatory socialization over the internet, which is free of any time and place restrictions. Social media is a kind of interactive communication and bilateral social network. Various communication contents can be shared and put into mass circulation easily and quickly through social media. These sharings are not only limited to individuals but also happen to groups, institutions, and different constitutions. Their contents consist of any type of written message, audio and video files. We are living in the social media era now. It is not surprising that social media which has extensive communication facilities and massive prevalence is used in politics. Therefore, the use of social media (Facebook) by political parties during the Turkish general elections held on June 7, 2015, has been chosen as our research subject. Four parties namely, AKP, CHP, MHP and HDP who have the majority of votes in Turkey and participate in elections in Konya have been selected for our study. Their provincial centers' and parliamentary candidates' use of social media (Facebook) on the last three days prior to the election have been examined and subjected to a qualitative analysis by means of content analysis.

Keywords—Social media, June 7 general elections, politics, Facebook.

I. INTRODUCTION

OUR age can be defined as the age of communication, telecommunication, and technology. Through the history, while every technological development transformed the course of production and consumption, it also signified a new life and new social relations. Whereas the steam engine appeared as a technical variance in the past, computer technologies and internet make the same life transforming and renewing influence at present. Along with the changing of technologies and technological devices used by the community, our life has been facilitated; yet the problems of the past have been replaced with the new ones. Today, in the age of the internet, we have growing generations being adapted to new life through social media, smartphones, e-mails, and chat. Web-based communication networks extending from trade to health; from banking to industrial production; from education to social sphere; from the political sphere to international relations, both define and transform our day. It constitutes a base for global capitalism, the global movement of capital, and flow of goods and services around the world. As Asa Briggs

Yasemin Gülşen Yılmaz and Süleyman Hakan Yılmaz is with Selçuk University, Communication Faculty, Konya, Turkey (e-mail: yasegulsen@hotmail.com, shakany@yahoo.com).

Muhammet Erbay is with Selçuk University, School of Foreign Languages, Konya, Turkey (e-mail: merbay@gmail.com).

and Peter Burke, in their book *Social History of the Media*, also underline “the story of global economics necessarily accompanies the story of global communications.” Major agent of global communication is also “internet” [1].

How the internet, which appears as the transforming factor, is defined? First, the internet is an electronic communication network interconnecting all the computers in the world. It is such a communication network that it cannot be controlled through a center. The Internet is a network architecture formed by thousands of autonomous computers, which can connect to each other in countless ways by overcoming electronic barriers [2]. The Internet and the Networks formed on which, is also a precursor of a new social structure reshaped around such networks. This structure can be called network society. A new society; network society, which is formed, communicating, developing a new language, getting socialized and politicized at times, and being transformed into a utopia without place and time through computers, fiber cables, internet technologies, monitor screens. As we also stated above, novelty is the computer networks established through the internet. The infrastructure of that network is built by fiber cables, telephone connections, satellite connections, and radio systems. While the internet is expanding its geographies of influence thanks to its new infrastructural facilities, it also offers users the opportunity to disseminate and Access the information. The internet is featured by speed, easy accessibility, and being economic [3]. It looks as if internet provided a substantial equality in the sphere of communication. On the other hand, freedom is called into question due to the existence of big capital behind the internet; and the emerging problems as the internet has been commercialized, and the fact that governments have been continuously trying to watch, record and control uncontrolled sphere; and resultantly, new forms of hegemony over the internet emerged.

The development process of the internet can be dated back to 1960s. Over the time from the 1960s to the present, the internet has been changed along with the developing technology, and it made available first to the military, and then to the state, and then to the individuals. Spread of websites and web portals increased the number of users and user activity each day [4].

The significance of internet at present day changed when the 3G technology, smartphones, and tablet computers put on the market. Such tools increased the speed of internet up to seconds, while facilitated personal access, and made the internet portable. Today internet is in the pocket; it is with you, wherever you are. Education and entertainment, which

were the basic functions of conventional media, has become the pioneer of new media with the incorporation of collaboration concept. New media defines and shapes the course of communication at present. New media term was coined for the information and communication-based research in the 1970s by researchers conducting social, psychological, economic, political, and cultural studies. However, the definition of the term in the 1970s has been broadened and changed with the computer and internet technologies, which gained momentum in 1990s [5]. A new media or new platforms also connote new classifications. The new is, in fact, a mixed structure including two different structures. Some part of this structure runs processes peculiar to computers, while another part contains structures such as communication tools (intercommunication, telecommunication, broadcasting, etc.). In that sense, new media is a concept with double meaning [6]. Again, according to Güngör, new media caused to the development of a mediated mass or individual (according to the circumstance) communication, as a new form of communication [7].

New media, which is shaped by the internet technology, includes CD-ROM, HTML, streaming media, digital video works, network applications, DVD video; and has been ever expanding geographically, with an ever increasing number of users [8]. Again, game consoles, iPods, small shaped data bank storages, and communicators and all similar digital tools are the technologies constituting the infrastructure of new media. They are the communication products brought under the title of new media. According to Binark, such technologies, which are ever increasing, have become an extension of the body [9].

Digital presentment, modularity, automation, variability, and code conversion can be listed as the five basic features of the new media. Those basic features define the new media and are underlying factors in the formation of it [10]. Above specified digital presentment is essential. New media is able to connect to digital networks through such a technical feature that is digital presentment. Such kind of connection offers users multimedia feature enabled by a flowing network running through bi-directional communication [11]. Besides, new media is interactive, fast, and unbounded; and the geographical distance is no longer a hindrance thanks to which; and it strengthens the communication; in other words, new media enriches classical mass communication media with computer technologies [12].

In order to get a deeper insight into new media, we need to look at traditional media. When we say, traditional media, newspapers, magazines, TV, and radio come to mind [13]. It is also called classical media or conventional media. Whereas creating content on conventional media incurs a certain cost, social media allows creating content at a very low cost [14]. Again, while the forms of conventional media listed on the previous line, can be obtained at different costs, social media offers those media forms altogether; and allows you to access them all on the same portal. Writing and sharing on social media, are social activities each [15]. Another new communication portal is social media, which represents the

evolution of the old through the time up to present [16]. In terms of the history of internet dating back to 1960s, social media marked 2000s by relating different geographies, different cultures, individuals to each other without time and space; and allowing them to communicate. In trendy words, it created new communication channels governing the flow of new life. It changed and redefined the content and form of socialization.

As a communication portal, social media enables communication between individuals, groups, communities, organizations, cultures, religions, nations, etc. It mediates the conveyance, circulation, and dissemination of message with multiple contents. Social media allows democracy at the courses of communication. Even reader of the message is turned into message creator in the next phase; as a result, this process became participatory and democratized [17].

Interconnection of computers on different parts of the world via internet turns into a portal of socialization through the sharings of computer users with each other. Computer network system is the new means of socialization. It is the means to share message [18]. Furthermore, even if it looks as if such a process of sharing, started with Facebook and Twitter as the most significant portals of communication, the process of such socialization started in 1971 when Ray Tomlinson sent the first e-mail from one computer to another via internet [19]. While classical media does not offer the possibility of such sharing and recycling, social media provides greater facilities for socialization.

Communication is first, a process enabling socialization of an individual. Therefore, communication is a social process/phenomenon. While communication is shaped by social relations, on the one hand, it influences the social relations on another hand [20]. Further, from a different angle, communication can be defined as the sharing by symbolizing the meanings, signs, patterns of behavior among the subjects [21]. The course of communication is shaped by the tool being utilized, as well as by cultural and social network; and it undergoes formal changes, having acquired new content through the history. Changing of communication also indicates the changing of individuals as well as social relations. In this sense, social media transformed forms of individual communication and social communication, and partly omitted traditional classical forms of communication. It even considerably influenced the meaning of public sphere by shifting, face-to-face, direct communication to virtual media.

The same as previous forms of communication, social media both defines technological possibilities of the age, and is the product of changed life and human relations because of industrialization, urbanism, and high technology. At present, it is the mean of socialization for the "new human" atomized by alienation, non-communication among the individuals, urban life, and hierarchical organization of the work. It is a way of socialization without time and space. It is the globalization of human relations. Today, when we say social media, Facebook, Twitter, Youtube, WhatsApp, Myspace, LinkedIn, Instagram, LiveJournal, Delicious, FriendFeed, Hi5, Slashdot, Digg, Reddit, StumbleUpon, Friendster, Tagged, Ning, Xanga,

Google+, Flickr, Pinterest and Bebo etc. first come to mind [22]. Each example of social media, functions as a platform for sharing different contents. Photo, sound, image (video), text, synchronized image and sound transfer, mutual messaging are enabled by social media forms; and an interactive way of communication is built during the process. All the listed social networking sites, allow users both to share and communicate at the same time. Social networks are built while the sharings are enriched by other sharings; and resultingly, thanks to those sharings, social media users can reach more and more people than the one we could ever imagine [23]. While the sharings gradually turn into a form of communication, courses of communication started on social networks, are transferred into life, and so become precursor of new formation and associations.

Social media serves as a platform for the socialization of the classical media. Moreover, according to Solis, in that way, interpersonal communication becomes easier, and so individuals are enabled to communicate to their social circles. New courses of social collaboration emerge. Mechanism of active dissemination also provides privileges to users [24].

Social media, which emerged with the advancement of web 2.0 technology, enabled a shift from reading only media to an interactive platform [25]. While the social media enables multi-communication, it also offers its users the opportunity to create media content individually, and to create and manage personal media that is the biggest novelty of social media. When the traditional media's massive aspect and corporate structure in production processes are considered, it can be argued that now we have a media content and form integrated with new media. Such an opportunity to create individual media content stimulated individual creativity, and it enabled overcoming capitalist structure of media and facilitated alternative publishing. Besides enabling content creation, social media also offers various facilities to its users; such as broadcasting a mass message. Your message on the same string swiftly reaches to different users, and a process of mass communication is formed along with the replies to the messages. This process is a bidirectional – symmetrical, fast, interactive, participatory process with a flexible structure. Synchronized transfer of the image and the voice is, in fact, an indicator of the change, which the face-to-face communication underwent through the time. While this process turns the reader-viewer into “reader-viewer,” it also underlined the “audiovisual” communication media [26]. Whereas the face-to-face communication has been shifted to a virtual platform, new forms of socialization including interpersonal and group communication appeared under various topics. Nazife Güngör lists the general structural features of social media as follows [27]:

- Interactivity
- Instantaneity
- Switchability of producer and consumer
- Not seeking commercial profit
- Economical
- Individualism and collectivism
- Small group communication

- Not requiring professionalism
- Disregarding hierarchical relations
- Cosmopolitan
- Chain communication
- Revisability of messages
- Multimedia feature
- Non-extended
- Beyond time
- Different ownership structure
- Providing substantial information

As it is evident, when we say social media, we mean communication portals different in terms of time use and scope. Among the social networks, Twitter and Facebook, come to fore particularly, in terms of both their number of users and their social impact. In our study, we examined the utilization of Facebook for political communication. Before treating the development of Facebook, we will have a glance at the Twitter, which has users as many as those of Facebook. Yet, we need, to begin with, the definition of social network. The social network is the name for all web-based services allowing individuals to create public/limitedly public profiles within a confined system; to publish the other users, they are connected to; to view other users' connections listed on the system, and to take a trip among them [28].

Twitter, is a social networking site. Its symbol is a bird named Larry and means twittering. It has been launched on date March 21, 2006, in San Francisco city, the state of California, United States; and has offices more than 25 over the world [29]. The general purpose of twitter is to offer people the opportunity to share their emotions, their thoughts, and experiences, which they find worth sharing with others in short expressions on the web; and this process is simple and repeatable like daily routines such as washing face, and having breakfast [30]. The site is a social and microblog site. Twitter users can share on the web any messages up to 140 characters. Particularly, instant messaging is followed by the followers, and a communication process is built with replies to those messages. Twitter which can be accessed by desktop PCs, and smartphones, is both portable and can be accessed at any time on different parts of the world thanks to mobile applications.

Social media also provides opportunities for political participation. The fact that social media is a significant medium for propaganda for politicians to reach masses makes social media an invaluable and effective medium of communication. Besides, even if the fact that social media user can make an instant political reaction, looks as “participation” for popular political culture, in fact, it only serves as a medium of “relief” for masses. However, the fact that protestors were organized through communication via social media during Arab Spring, that is demonstrations, protests, civil commotion, and armed conflicts emerged in Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, Syria, Bahrai, Algeria, Jordan and Yemen in big scale, and in Mauretania, Suudi Arabia, Oman, Iraq, Lebanon and Morocco in small scale, attracted attention to social media. Similarly, it is evident that during “Occupy Wall Street” movement in USA, and Gezi Demonstrations in

Taksim, Istanbul, and social media became prominent in the sphere of communication and organization [31].

Before discussing the power and significance of social media in politics and political participation, we need to touch on foundation and development process of Facebook, which constitutes a field of examination in our study. As stated above, Facebook is a social networking site intended for and enabling people's communication and exchange of information. It is for people to communicate and share information, photos, videos, etc. with their friends via Facebook Inc. [32]. On date February 4, 2004, it was founded by Mark Zuckerberg, who was then a student of Harvard University, class of 2006. Zuckerberg founded Facebook primarily for Harvard students [33]. Facebook is among the most visited websites in the world. According to Alexa statistics, Facebook is the second most visited website in the world by August 31, 2014. Further, it is the most visited website in Egypt; the second in USA, Australia, Turkey, Panama, and Norway; and the third in Canada, South Africa, United Kingdom, and Sweden; and is globally the most visited website by 2012. Facebook was named after "paper Facebook," which is a personal profile form which American universities have their students, instructors, and employees fill in. Now, Facebook has more than 1 billion users. In technical terms, Facebook is identified by web authorities as one of most successful Web 2.0 applications. Facebook is available in languages German, Czech, Simplified Chinese, Traditional Chinese, Hong Kong Chinese, Danish, Finnish, French, Welsh, Dutch, Spanish, Swedish, Italian, Japanese, Catalan, Korean, Polish, Norwegian Bokmal, Brazilian Portuguese, Azerbaijani, Albanian, Thai, Slovenian, Romanian, Norsk, Hungarian, Galician, Turkish, Kurdish, and Russian [34].

When we say the use of social networks and social media in politics, we are talking about a new process of communication. While our country has newly started to use Social Networks as a medium of the organization, there is already an organization of a political kind abroad. In that sense, Barack Obama- the president of United States, constitutes a good example, he densely used the social media during presidential elections of 2008. Of course, heading off a personal political organization, political parties make significant progress in election campaigns, as much as they employ organization on the social network. Chains, which are formed by people influencing each other, and by a grouping of people with a similar stand, will be a part of the major impact during the campaigns. The trend of following as the basis of social networks plays a key role in that sense [35].

Barack Obama, who was a presidential candidate during the elections of the USA in 2008, won 52% votes – which none of the presidential candidates from Democratic Party had won in 30 years. Social media played an important part in such success of Obama. When Obama was organizing his campaign for the elections, he realized that young people were using social media rather than reading newspaper or books; so he structured his campaign accordingly. In the scope of that strategy, Obama used social media platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter rather than using traditional

media; and so reached to the electorate through social media. This was named as the new media victory after election results [36]. Similarly, as he did during the presidential elections of 2008; Obama actively used social media also during the electoral process of 2012. Declaring his candidacy through a video streamed on the internet during elections in 2012, Obama effectively used also different platforms such as Tumblr, Klout, Pinterest and Instagram, in addition to Facebook, Twitter and YouTube for his campaign of the second term; as a result social media served as the factor empowering him mostly also during second elections. Obama's success in social media reflected credit on the congress as well. In the USA, where the bicameral system, including the House of Representatives and the Senate, is executed, while the number of social media users of House of Representatives with 435 seats was 38% in 2011, it increased to 98% in January 2013. Facebook and Twitter, which have 40 million users in our country, were for the first time actively used during general elections of 2011 in Turkey. For the first time, it was in June 2011, when social media was used as an important medium of propaganda and communication in Turkey, during the election campaigns conducted for electing members of the assembly for the 24th term of the Grand National Assembly of Turkey (TBMM). During that period of elections, parties, party leaders, deputy candidates, also benefited from traditional media [37]. From the General Elections on June 12, up to present, social media became more and more popular in the political sphere. Local elections in 2014 and presidential elections were the new occasions for the use of social media. Lastly, parties and deputy candidates during general elections of 2015/ 7 attracted attention with their use of social media. Accordingly, in this study, we examined the social media use by 4 political parties, which passed the threshold in the case of Konya province, during the elections of June 7, 2015.

II. AIM OF THE STUDY

In our study, in the case of the metropolitan city of Konya, form, and frequency of social media use by four big political parties for the publicity of their candidates, and party propaganda activities during political campaigns they run for the General Elections of June 7, 2015. Within the scope of this study, social media pages belonging to Justice and Development Party (AKP), Republican People's Party (CHP), Nationalist Movement Party (MHP) and People's Democratic Party (HDP) have been analyzed.

III. METHODOLOGY

Content analysis method has been employed. A number of the messages, the number of followers of the political parties, the number of participants, and the shares on the social media has been both examined quantitatively, and the related data has been analyzed. Numeric data has been given on the graphs, and how the parties use social media have been outlined. This study is confined to the days 4,5, and 6 of June prior to the General Elections of June 7, 2015. During the last

two days before the election, the pre-election propaganda was most densely made, and especially June 6 is significant as it is the last day before the elections.

IV. STUDY

Under the study, following has been concluded with reference to the number of posts, comments and likes on Facebook for AKP, CHP, MHP, and HDP, during the dates 4-5-6 of June prior to June 7 General Elections;

- Facebook consumption by Provincial Organization of AKP in Konya is the highest, with 21 posts. AKP is followed by Provincial Organizations of CHP, HDP, and MHP in Konya, respectively with 13, 5 and 4 posts. With regard to sharing photos on Facebook, CHP takes the lead with 73 photos; and CHP is followed by MHP, AKP, and HDP, respectively with 44, 20 and 17 photos.
- When looked at the number of likes, that is the way followers of the page express their appreciation of the page, AKP is ranked first with 924 likes, and is followed by HDP, MHP, CHP, respectively with 584, 181, and 80 likes. Here, the number of likes is significant not because people liked the page, but as it indicates the activeness of those who express their sympathy for the parties. Here, another striking indication is how successful are the provincial organizations in mobilizing people.
- With regard to the number of shares, AKP is well ahead of others with 924 shares and is followed by HDP, MHP, and CHP, respectively with 32, 4 and 1 shares.
- As for the number of comments, it is evident that AKP is again well ahead with 140 comments, whereas there are 4 comments on the Facebook page of HDP, and no comments on that of CHP and MHP. Following conclusion has been made with reference to the messages that parties posted on their pages;
- Facebook page of Provincial Organization of AKP in Konya was used for announcing activities of both the provincial organization and headquarter of the party. Moreover, slogans for motivating their followers for the elections were posted. In addition, the activities of provincial leader and of deputy candidates were made public on the Facebook page. Video, poster, and slogan draw attention among the propaganda tools used for the elections. In addition, through the page, the public has been called to the party rally held by Prime Minister Ahmet Davutoğlu in Konya during the electoral process.
- Provincial Organization of CHP in Konya published election campaign speech by Kemal Kılıçdaroğlu- General President of CHP on the Facebook page. Besides, selection of news from the newspapers Cumhuriyet and Sözcü were shared on the Facebook page. Further, election campaigns run in the province by deputy candidates of CHP were published on the page. In addition, the election campaigns by women's branch of CHP, as well as CHP's election campaigns in the towns were published on the Facebook page of the provincial organization.

- HDP shared the news on the rally in Van on Facebook. Election speeches by Figen Yüksekdağ and Selahattin Demirtaş - co-presidents of the party, were also published on the Facebook page of the provincial organization. In addition, rally in Amed (Diyarbakır), was shared on the page. Lastly, a message of condolences for Akif Satılmış was the driver working for HDP and was killed in the town Karlıova of Bingöl Province.
- Provincial organization of MHP in Konya allowed space for introducing the deputy candidates of Konya. A music concert by Mustafa Yıldızoğlu in Ereğli Township was one of the postings on the page. In addition, election campaigns by MHP in the towns of Konya were published on the Facebook page.

TABLE I
 TOTAL NUMBER OF POSTS, PHOTOS, LIKES, SHARES, AND COMMENTS ON THE OFFICIAL FACEBOOK PAGE BY PROVINCIAL ORGANIZATION OF AKP BETWEEN THE DATES OF 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

AKP	Number of posts	Photos	Likes	Shares	Comments
4.06.2015	7	7	1958	320	25
5.06.2015	6	6	916	97	26
6.06.2015	8	7	5948	507	89
TOTAL	21	20	8822	924	140

Fig. 1 Total Number of posts, Photos, Likes, Shares and Comments on the official Facebook page by Provincial Organization of AKP between the dates of 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

Fig. 2 Total Number of posts, Photos, Likes, Shares and Comments on the official Facebook page by Provincial Organization of CHP between the dates of 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

TABLE II

TOTAL NUMBER OF PHOTOS, LIKES, SHARES, AND COMMENTS ON THE OFFICIAL FACEBOOK PAGE BY PROVINCIAL ORGANIZATION OF CHP BETWEEN THE DATES OF 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

CHP	Number of posts	Photos	Likes	Shares	Comments
4.06.2015	2	11	24	0	0
5.06.2015	8	60	33	1	0
6.06.2015	3	2	23	0	0
TOTAL	13	73	80	1	0

TABLE III

TOTAL NUMBER OF PHOTOS, LIKES, SHARES, AND COMMENTS ON THE OFFICIAL FACEBOOK PAGE BY PROVINCIAL ORGANIZATION OF HDP BETWEEN THE DATES OF 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

HDP	Number of posts	Photos	Likes	Shares	Comments
4.06.2015	1	1	45	0	2
5.06.2015	2	3	228	15	1
6.06.2015	2	13	311	17	1
TOTAL	5	17	584	32	4

Fig. 3 Total Number of posts, Photos, Likes, Shares and Comments on the official Facebook page by Provincial Organization of HDP between the dates of 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

TABLE IV

TOTAL NUMBER OF PHOTOS, LIKES, SHARES, AND COMMENTS ON THE OFFICIAL FACEBOOK PAGE BY PROVINCIAL ORGANIZATION OF MHP BETWEEN THE DATES OF 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

MHP	Number of posts	Photos	Likes	Shares	Comments
4.06.2015	0	0	0	0	0
5.06.2015	4	44	181	4	0
6.06.2015	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	4	44	181	4	0

V. CONCLUSION

The significance of social media in our daily life has been ever growing, along with the increase in the use of social media in recent years. Social media is a platform for communication, and a web-based tool-organizing communication between individuals, groups, institutions, etc. Social media is not only a medium of socialization but also a multi-media platform where messages are transmitted, texts are shared, videos are posted; and where it is possible to share photos. In terms of the opportunities it offers, it is not possible for the institution of politics not to realize it and not to devise it in the political sphere. Social media, which was actively used by Barack Obama-Presidential candidate for the

Presidential Elections of United States of America in 2008, is widely used today in different parts of the world for the purpose of political campaigns, in addition to corporate and personal use. Social media was first used in our country during the process of General Elections in 2011, and from then until Parliamentary General Elections of June 7, 2015, established itself in our life, as a major means of propaganda and political communication.

Fig. 4 Total Number of posts, Photos, Likes, Shares and Comments on the official Facebook page by Provincial Organization of MHP between the dates of 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

TABLE V

TOTAL NUMBER OF PHOTOS, LIKES, SHARES AND COMMENTS ON THE OFFICIAL FACEBOOK PAGE BY PROVINCIAL ORGANIZATION OF AKP, CHP, HDP AND MHP BETWEEN THE DATES OF 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

	Number of posts	Photos	Likes	Shares	Comments
AKP	21	20	8822	924	140
CHP	13	73	80	1	0
HDP	5	17	584	32	4
MHP	4	44	181	4	0
TOTAL	43	154	9.667	961	144

Fig. 5 Total Number of posts, Photos, Likes, Shares and Comments on the official Facebook page by Provincial Organization of AKP, CHP, HDP and MHP between the dates of 4.06.2015-6.06.2015

Our research covering electoral campaigns on Facebook by the parties in Konya during three days 4-5-6 of June before the Parliamentary General Elections of June 7, affirmed that significance of social media as a medium of political communication had been gradually growing. Through the social media, political parties can more easily transmit their political messages as well as their campaigns to masses; and

can easily have intercommunication with segments of society, which have a similar stand with their party. During the upcoming period, the significance of using social media will grow further in the political sphere as well. If the political institutions and their candidates develop a strategy of communication on social media and have a policy of communication, they will be more successful in this process. While they are taking advantage of social media, they will avoid potential misfortunes of communication.

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